

Protection of Traditional Knowledge : Global perspectives on Initiatives and Challenges

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Through multiple generations, traditional knowledge (TK) has been transmitted, making it a rich and diverse resource. It has its roots in local cultures and indigenous populations' knowledge and practices. The need to safeguard traditional knowledge (TK) within the framework of intellectual property rights (IPR) has increased due to the quick acceleration of globalization and commercialization. TK owned by local or indigenous communities is becoming more and more susceptible to theft. Since it has long been acknowledged as being vital, traditional knowledge (TK) is subject to a number of international accords that address related concerns. The paper examines challenges, procedures, and global initiatives to protect traditional knowledge and local communities' rights in global perspective.